

Synthesis of 6-Substituted-phenoxy-6,7-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[*c,h*]-[1,2,5,7,6]dithiadiazaphosphonine-6-oxides

M. S. R. NAIDU*, E. O. JOHN BULL and M. V. S. R. PRASAD

Department of Chemistry, S. V. University, Tirupatl-517 502

Manuscript received 27 March 1992, accepted 15 May 1992

In continuation of our studies on the chemistry of organophosphorus heterocyclic compounds¹, we now report the synthesis of the title compounds containing sulphur, nitrogen and phosphorus in the nine-membered ring.

Synthesis of these compounds (1a–k) have been accomplished by the condensation of 2,2'-diaminodiphenyl disulphide with substituted phenylphosphorodichloridates in refluxing toluene (Scheme 1). The compounds (Table 1) were found to be insoluble in most of the organic solvents. However, analytically pure compounds were obtained by repeated trituration with warm toluene, tetrahydrofuran and methanol.

- | | |
|--|-----------------------------|
| 1a; R=H | g; R=2-Cl |
| b; R=2-CH ₃ | h; R=4-Cl |
| c; R=3-CH ₃ | i; R=4-Cl-2-CH ₃ |
| d; R=4-CH ₃ | j; R=4-Cl-3-CH ₃ |
| e; R=2,5-(CH ₃) ₂ | k; R=2,4-Cl ₂ |
| f; R=3,4-(CH ₃) ₂ | |

Scheme 1

In ir spectra, the absorption due to $\nu_{P=O}$ is observed at lower frequency than the expected region² indicating the involvement of the oxygen atom of phosphoryl group in the hydrogen bonding with amidic hydrogen atom. ν_{P-NH} exhibited³ band at 3 345–3 320 cm^{-1} . Mass spectra for a few of these

compounds have been recorded and no $M^{+\bullet}$ ion is observed. However, the appearance of an ion at m/z 278 with low intensity (Chart 1) confirms the presence of dibenzodithiadiazaphosphonine ring system in these compounds (1a–k).

Chart 1

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir (KBr) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer PE 781 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D 300 instrument at 70 eV.

Substituted phenylphosphorodichloridates and 2,2'-diaminodiphenyl disulphide were prepared by known procedure.

6-Phenoxy-6,7-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[c, h][1,2,5,7,6]-dithiadiazaphosphonine-6-oxide (1a): Phenylphosphorodichloridate (2.12 g, 0.01 mol) in dry toluene (20 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of 2,2'-diaminodiphenyl disulphide (2.48 g, 0.01 mol) in toluene (40 ml) in the presence of a slow stream of nitrogen. The reaction mixture was reflux for 4 h. The completion of the reaction was noted by the absence of the evolution of HCl. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and the resulting solid was washed thoroughly with hot methanol and tetrahydrofuran (2.38 g, 57%) m.p. 228–30°; ν_{\max} 1 140 (P=O) and 3 335 cm^{-1} (P–NH); m/z 278 (1.3), 247 (99.6), 141 (15.2), 104 (100.0) and 77 (50.0).

This general procedure was used for the preparation of other compounds (1b–k): 1b (46%), m.p. 210–12°; c (48%), 219–21°; d (49%), 216–18°; e (46%), 206–09°; f (45%), 220–21°; g (57%),

217–19°; h (48%), 215–17°; i (47%), 204–07°; j (58%), 210–13°; k (46%) 206–07°. All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (E.O.J.B.) is thankful to U.G.C. and the other (M.V.S.R.P.) to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of fellowships.

References

1. M. S. R. NAIDU and C. N. RAJU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, 27, 88; 1989, 28, 87; M. S. R. NAIDU, E. O. J. BULL and C. N. RAJU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1990, 29, 691.
2. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1958, p. 249.
3. N. B. COLTHUP, N. H. DALY and S. E. WIBERLY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1964, p. 189.